

Performance evaluation of three-stage anaerobic digestion (AD) for stabilization of fruit and vegetable waste (FVW)

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Abstract : Anaerobic Digestion (AD) can be considered as the most appropriate Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) technique, since it is capable of not only stabilizing a significant quantity of generated waste at once but also ensures generation of biogas, which is a non-conventional source of energy. A major part (40–50%) of the generated Organic Fraction of the Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW) is constituted of Fruit and Vegetable Waste (FVW). In the present study, an attempt has been made to understand the performance of a three-stage lab-scale anaerobic digester for stabilizing FVW. FVW was procured from numerous households and from the guest-house kitchen of Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur (IESTS). The feasibility of FVW to undergo anaerobic digestion was established after physical characterization of the procured FVW on individual and composite basis. The performance evaluation of the lab-scale AD system was based on the batch study results of pH, alkalinity and soluble Chemical Oxygen Demand (sCOD). Mesophilic temperature regime was selected for carrying out all the batches. The following substrate utilization rates (k) were obtained : 0.168 d^{-1} , 0.6 d^{-1} , and 0.56 d^{-1} , respectively for the hydrolytic, the acidogenic, and the methanogenic reactors.

Keywords : Three-stage AD, lab-scale, OFMSW, batch study, COD reduction, kinetics.

Introduction

The day-to-day increase in the generation of municipal solid waste (MSW), especially in the metropolitan, urban and suburban areas have resulted into the development of AD as one of the most efficient methodologies for managing the solid waste problem. The improvement in the standard of living as well as the uncontrolled population growth can be accounted for this unprecedented increase in the MSW rate, which was found to be $0.77 \text{ kg/person/day}$ in 23 developing countries all over the world¹. The process of AD results in the volumetric reduction of the huge quantity of the generated MSW, thereby striking a balance between the generation and the stabilization rate of MSW. AD of OFMSW primarily involves a series of metabolic reactions (hydrolysis,

acidogenesis, acetogenesis and methanogenesis) controlled by diverse microbial populations to convert the organic waste into biogas and other energy-rich organic compounds as end products²⁻⁶. In other words, the process of anaerobic decomposition has the potential to provide useful products such as biogas, methane, H_2 , and the sludge generated is also used as an organic amendment⁷ for soil. Besides these, the process of AD doesn't require oxygen supply^{8,9} and there is no dependency on fossil fuel for energy consumption¹⁰. Hence, this process is becoming particularly conspicuous in the field of energy production nowadays. Other conventional processes, which are in practice for managing MSW, include sanitary landfilling, composting, thermal incineration, and pyrolysis/gasification¹¹.

In comparison to sanitary landfilling, AD of OFMSW have certain advantages such as : (a) in case of sanitary landfilling, the requirement of land is much greater than that of AD of OFMSW; (b) the closed environment, in case of AD of OFMSW, eliminates all the possibilities of uncontrolled release of gases into the atmosphere whereas in case of sanitary landfilling there is always a possibility of uncontrolled release of landfill gases into the atmosphere, which may potentially cause a dangerous condition by contributing to the green-house effect in the atmosphere¹²; (c) the chances of uncontrolled leachate movement is prevented in case of AD of OFMSW, since this is carried out in a closed system, which eventually safeguards the surrounding environment; (d) prevention of the breeding and harboring of disease vectors courtesy the aforementioned closed functioning environment; (e) unlike sanitary landfilling, no post closure management is required.

Very similar to sanitary landfilling, one of the major problems associated with aerobic composting, which is mostly popular, is the biodegradation of organic solid waste (especially residues of plant and animal origin) in the open, which causes effusion of offensive odors and breeding of various disease vectors. These increase the possibility of human health hazards, since the public hygiene gets compromised. Anaerobic composting does overcome the problem of offensive odor effusion, but both aerobic and anaerobic composting necessitate large spaces for operation alike sanitary landfilling. In addition, composting is applicable to relatively lesser types of organic solid waste, such as, yard waste, commingled MSW, separated MSW, cattle dung, etc.¹², compared to AD, which can treat liquid organic waste and varieties of organic solid waste simultaneously with better efficiency, in terms of process stability. Also, the efficiency of AD, with regards to quality and marketability of the end products, is notably far-better than composting, whose end product can be only used up as a soil conditioner after conditioning.

The major problem associated with the existing thermal conversion techniques for MSWM, is the need for high energy input. According to Singh *et al.* (2011), incineration occurs at temperatures be-

tween 750°C and 1000°C; pyrolysis occurs at three different temperature ranges i.e. between 277°C and 627°C (conventional pyrolysis), between 577°C and 977°C (fast pyrolysis), and between 777°C and 1027°C; and gasification takes place at a temperature range between 100°C and 977°C. Burning the MSW at such high temperature ranges not only demands the use of expensive set-up and appropriate pollution control accessories, but employment of skilled/dedicated personnel who are capable of operating such sophisticated set-up is equally important. In addition, the burning of MSW at such high temperatures lead to the evolution of various air pollutants, such as NO_x, SO_x, CO_x, etc., which despite taking appropriate controlling measures may end up polluting the air-quality surrounding the treatment plant. The energy generation at the end may well match up with that of the AD process but the involvement of a comparatively higher capital cost makes thermal conversion economically infeasible. Furthermore, there are clear technical limitations visible in case of thermal conversion techniques with regards to simultaneous management of two or more types of organic waste. Unlike AD, where treatment of OFMSW can be simultaneously carried out with other types of organic waste, such as abattoir waste, municipal wastewater, cattle dung, thermal conversion techniques are mainly capable of treating only one of type waste, whose moisture content is significantly low¹³. Undoubtedly, thermal conversion is not only cumbersome but techno-economically infeasible in the long-run.

Numerous problems associated with one-stage and two-stage AD systems have led to the development of the three-stage AD system. Three-stage AD systems are those where the three major phases of hydrolysis, acidogenesis/acetogenesis, and methanogenesis are made to occur in three different chambers connected in series. Single-stage AD systems are those where all the aforesaid major phases occur inside a single chamber. In case of two-stage AD systems, the hydrolysis and the acidogenesis phases occur in a single chamber and the methanogenesis occur in a second chamber connected to the first in series. In single-stage AD systems, the OFMSW undergo conversion

from solid to liquid to gaseous state inside a single chamber, which is why the adjustment of pH desirable to each phase becomes extremely cumbersome. It can be observed from past literatures that the suitable pH range for the acidogens is in between 5.0 and 6.5^{14,15}. In case of the hydrolytic organisms the suitable pH range is in between 4.0 and 5.5, and the methanogens the optimum working pH range is in between 6.8 and 7.8. Furthermore, the methanogens do not compete for attachment spaces unlike the hydrolytic and the acidogenic microorganisms, which need large surface areas to colonize¹⁶.

In the event of separating the hydrolytic phase from the acidogenic phase, enhancement in the decoupling of hydrolysis and acidogenesis occurs. Decoupling¹⁷, which occurs when there is a change in operational condition pertaining to hydraulic retention time (HRT), ensures better degradation of solid substrate present in OFMSW to particulate organic matter via hydrolysis, and subsequent conversion of those particulate matter into volatile fatty acid (VFA) via acidogenesis¹⁸. It is evident that the HRT, which is defined as the time duration during which the food remains in contact with the microbes, in case of hydrolysis, which is the rate-limiting step in AD, has to be kept greater than the HRT pertaining to the acidogenic phase. Also, if the hydrolytic phase is separated from the acidogenic phase high OLRs can be chosen since the HRTs for the hydrolytic and the acidogenic phase can be kept different. Substrates which are easily decomposed by certain group of microbes can be loaded into a chamber at high OLRs and under short HRTs if only the major phases are operated separately. For instance, hydrolysis takes longer time than methanogenesis, which in turn is slower than acidogenesis. Similarly, the need for choosing a certain mixing intensity varies with the type of phase. For instance, hydrolysis demands rapid mixing in order to facilitate degradation of solid organic substrates, efficiently remove pathogens, and minimize channeling. On the other hand, acidogenesis demands slow mixing so as to disperse the excess accumulation of volatile fatty acids (VFAs). Methanogenesis, on the other hand, does not necessitate mixing since it causes disruption of syntrophic

association between various microbes in flocs (also known as juxtapositioning)¹⁹. Separating the three phases presents with the option of choosing different types of mixing optimum to each phase.

Thus there are several advantages of three-stage AD systems such as, convenient monitoring of the individual phases under batch mode of operations, easier handling of the digesters with regards to organic loading and sample collection, and increased rates of hydrolysis, acidogenesis and methanogenesis without affecting the pH optimum to each phase. These apart the chances of inhibition to each phase, caused by the increase in concentrations of several constituents such as VFA, sulfate, phosphate, nitrogen, etc., get greatly reduced in case of three-stage digester owing to separate container system. However, in case of a three-stage AD system maintaining a fixed temperature for all the three stages is challenging unless all the three containment structures are kept in a single enclosure. Not only that, literatures²⁰ have showed that AD of source sorted OFMSW from fruit and vegetable markets²¹ and other types of high solid waste are most suitable for two-stage AD. Further, one-stage AD systems are mostly convenient on an industrial scale due to cheaper maintenance and investment cost²².

The present study evaluates the performance of a three-stage lab-scale anaerobic digester using FVW. The reason can be attributed to the fact that the availability, collection and handling of FVW^{23,24} are very much easy compared to other different types of OFMSW. Not only that, past studies²⁵⁻²⁷ have also revealed FVW to be the most suitable among the different types of other OFMSW, in terms of the rapidity rendered to the AD process. As such, physical characterization of the procured FVW was carried out in order to establish its feasibility to undergo AD. The performance evaluation of the three-stage lab-scale anaerobic digester was based on the batch study results of pH, alkalinity, and COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand).

Materials and methods :

Selection of FVW and their characterization :

Characterization was done using FVW since the

availability, collection and handling of FVW are easier compared to other different types of OFMSW. The selection of the different fruit and vegetable items for the purpose of characterization was based on the reciprocal of their unit prices. Items with high unit prices were discarded. In the end 12 items were chosen namely, potato, serpent gourd, ash gourd, okra, cowpea, ribbed gourd, bitter gourd, gourd, papaya, brinjal/eggplant, cucumber and guava and different parameters, such as bulk density, specific gravity, moisture content, loss of moisture, fixed solid, and volatile solid were determined under individual and compo-site basis. A range for all the parameters were established/specified by obtaining at least two sets of data for each of the 12 FVW items under individual and composite basis.

After procuring a particular item it was chopped into small uniform pieces and was divided into four separate fractions for the determination of the aforementioned parameters. While determining parameters for a composite fraction (either composite vegetable wastes or composite fruit wastes) a few set of items from the vegetable waste category or from the fruit waste category were chosen based on the reciprocal of their unit prices and they were mixed up uniformly after chopping into small pieces. Again, the chopped pieces were divided into four separate fractions and it was ensured that each fraction was homogeneous in terms of the distribution of the fruit or vegetable items, which were chosen for the determination of the composite characteristics. The division was made in accordance with the measurement of the following sets : (1) specific gravity and bulk density, (2) loss of moisture, and (3) moisture content, fixed solids and volatile solids content. Another fraction was used for the purpose of determining the hydrolysis potential of the particular item or the composite fraction.

For determination of specific gravity and bulk density water displacement method was chosen, whereby a pre-weighed fraction of the waste item was carefully transferred into a 1 L measuring cylinder containing 500 ml water. The displaced volume of water was noted, and it was carefully and slowly transferred from the 1 L measuring cylinder to a 50

ml measuring cylinder, for precise measurement purpose, such that the meniscus in the 1 L measuring cylinder once again reached 500 ml with the fraction of the waste item still inside. The mass of the fraction, which was pre-weighed, divided by the displaced volume of water, gave the bulk density and the corresponding specific gravity. For determination of the loss of moisture, another fraction of the waste item was pre-weighed and it was kept inside the hot air oven for one hour at 105°C. After one hour, the FVW fraction from the hot air oven was transferred to a desiccator for it to cool down to room temperature. The relative humidity and surrounding temperature, at the time (July to September) of characterization, were observed to be $75 \pm 15\%$ and $32 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ respectively. Thereafter, the measured loss in weight gave the loss of moisture. For determination of the moisture content another pre-weighed fraction was allowed to dry completely at 105°C inside the hot air oven. Following this, the dried FVW fraction was transferred to a desiccator for it to cool down to room temperature. Thereafter, the measured loss in weight gave the moisture content of that waste item. Using the same fraction which was used for measuring the loss of moisture, the fixed solid content of the waste item was determined. This was done by putting the fraction inside the muffle furnace at 550°C for approximately 8–10 min, after the calculation of the loss of moisture had been performed. Complete combustion was ensured by exposing the entire surface area of the waste item inside the muffle furnace. The ash content gave the fixed solid content, which was determined by weighing the amount of ash left. The result of the subtraction between the initial weight (fresh fraction prior to putting in the hot air oven) and the final weight gave the volatile solid content.

The importance of choosing the aforementioned parameters for the purpose of characterization can be explained from the point of view that those parameters play a key role in not only deciding how the AD process should occur, in terms of the process rapidity, but also on the nature and quality of the stabilized volume after the waste has undergone AD. Apart from that those parameters also help us to get

a clear idea as to whether or not that particular waste type is compatible for AD or any another classical method of waste stabilization, keeping in mind the modality of the usage of the waste following its stabilization.

Analytical procedure :

Performance evaluation of the three-stage lab-scale mesophilic anaerobic digester was based on the following parameters : (1) pH, (2) Total Alkalinity, and (3) COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand). The parameters were measured as per the methods described in the APHA Standard Methods²⁸. It is noteworthy to mention the importance of pH measurement in our study because it not only indicated the increase or decrease in the VFA concentrations necessary for the various biochemical processes in the three reactors to occur, but also gave a fair idea regarding the stability of the digester as-a-whole. The hydrolytic, the acidogenic and the methanogenic bacteria are very much sensitive to pH, with the methanogenic microbes being the most sensitive amongst the three. Slightest of change from the desirable pH range may result in the impediment of the microbial activities in all the three systems. An increase in the undissociated VFA concentration usually results in the penetration of the undissociated volatile acids into the bacterial cells without any resistance. In case of the methanogens the pH inside them being higher than the pH of the medium is affected by the release of protons of the acids. This result in the formation of ATP and consequently other processes inside the cytoplasm inhibit the methane formation. Methane formation is very much essential to the growth of methanogenic bacteria.

Alkalinity, expressed in mg/L as CaCO₃, indicates the buffering capacity of an AD system. Stable digester operations can be achieved by maintaining the alkalinity in the desired range. In an AD system, alkalinity gets contributed by the formation of CO₂, ammonia and bicarbonate¹³. The system pH is basically an indication of the CO₂ in gas phase and bicarbonate alkalinity in the liquid phase. The buffering capacity, which is often referred to as the alkalinity, of an AD system is thus an indication of the

equilibrium between CO₂ and bicarbonate ions. Digester imbalance is best observed via alkalinity/buffering capacity, since a drop in system pH is an occurrence which happens after VFA accumulation has significantly reduced the system alkalinity. In an AD system the total alkalinity should be desirably above 7400 mg/L as CaCO₃ for smooth digester operations. The bicarbonate alkalinity, which is believed to represent the actual buffering capacity of an AD system and is the main source of carbon for the autotrophic methanogens, should be desirably above 2400 mg/L for stable digester operations.

A drop in the buffering capacity can be countered by the reduction in OLR, measured by the influent COD concentration. Other than that, addition of strong bases and salts of carbonate can also be done since this will result in the removal of CO₂ by converting it into bicarbonate. The initial/influent COD concentrations for the acidogenic system should be desirably higher than the methanogenic system, which in turn should have an OLR greater than the hydrolytic system. Substrate utilization is indicated by the difference in the initial and the final COD values in a batch operation. Closed reflux method, conforming to APHA Standard Methods²⁸, was chosen for measuring the soluble COD in all the three systems.

Brief description of the reactor set-up :

The fabrication of the three-stage anaerobic reactor was done in the Environmental Engineering Laboratory, IESTS. It consisted of a semi-anaerobic hydrolytic chamber connected to an anaerobic acidogenic chamber and a strictly anaerobic methanogenic chamber. Apart from that, a gas collection arrangement was also made and the temperature in the methanogenic chamber was maintained at 40±2°C (mesophilic regime) using a heater. The operating temperature of the hydrolytic and the acidogenic chambers were maintained at room temperature, which was 32±2°C (mesophilic regime). A stirrer was attached with the hydrolytic chamber in order to prevent inhibition due to foaming caused by the formation of propionic acid, and complete dispersion of the solid substrates. The chamber volumes were decided depending on the sub-

strate utilization rates of the individual systems (hydrolysis, acidogenesis and methanogenesis) as found out from the available literatures. The detailed description of the three-stage anaerobic reactor is mentioned in the following section.

The laboratory-scale three-stage anaerobic digester (Fig. 1) was fabricated using two 10 L chambers, one 15 L container, one 22 L container and four 5 L containers. The 8 containers were connected sequentially with the two 10 L containers first followed by the 15 L container and the 22 L container, on one side, and on the opposite side the remaining four 5 L containers were connected to each other for the purpose of gas collection and purification. The two 10 L containers, dedicated to hydrolysis, of which the first container had two chambers separated by a mesh, on top of which the solid FVW got stored and the liquid or the hydrolyzed portion got accumulated at the bot-

tom. The second of the two 10 L containers, to which the stirrer was attached, was filled up with the accumulated liquid or hydrolyzed product from the first container. The third 15 L container, a dedicated acidogenesis chamber, was filled up with contents from the second container where hydrolysis was allowed to occur. Initially at the start-up phase of the three-stage reactor the acidogenic chamber was filled up with the hydrolyzed portion of the different FVW fraction, which were used for hydrolysis study. The fourth 22 L container, a dedicated methanogenic chamber, was fitted with a heating arrangement using a heater that was placed inside the chamber, with the temperature control panel on the outside. Since the heater was in direct contact with methanogenic content, the material of the heater body was made of an inert material in order to impede any type of reaction with the methanogenic content.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram showing the hydrolytic, the acidogenic and the methanogenic system followed by the gas-collection set-up.

For the purpose of collecting only the generated methane, the biogas coming out of the methanogenic reactor it was first directed to a 5 L container containing 5% KOH solution so that the CO₂ present in the biogas was eliminated. Thereafter, the biogas was sent to the second 5 L chamber which had 10% (CH₃COOH)₂Pb in order to eliminate the H₂S from the generated biogas. Following the removal of both CO₂ and H₂S the biogas containing CH₄ was directed to the third 5 L chamber, atop of which a gas escaping valve was attached, filled with commercially available distilled water. The last 5 L chamber was also filled with commercially available distilled water. As methane got collected in the third 5 L chamber, displacement of water from the third 5 L chamber to the ultimate 5 L chamber occurred. The generated biogas was thus allowed to escape from the system through the valve attached atop of the penultimate 5 L chamber following displacement of water.

Acclimation of the three-stage anaerobic digester :

The start-up of the methanogenic chamber was mainly done using wastewater sludge, as the seed, and it was inoculated using cow-dung. The cow-dung and the wastewater sludge were mixed up in a bucket and they were diluted with a certain volume of water. Thereafter the entire content was loaded in the methanogenic chamber. The purpose of selecting wastewater sludge is that it not only contains the necessary anaerobic bacteria but also has the essential nutrients required for the purpose of the anaerobic bacterial growth. The reason for mixing it with cow dung can be explained from the point of view that cow dung has anaerobic microorganisms, which can be found in the rumen of cow and other ruminant animals and, which are capable of bringing about the breakdown of cellulose and carbohydrates present in FVW. These microbes are capable of converting the acetate part into carbon dioxide and methane²⁹. In short, the cow dung had the methane producing microorganisms which were acclimated using the wastewater sludge, containing the essential nutrients.

For the purpose of starting up the acidogenic chamber, hydrolyzed products of the FVW fraction that

was used for the purpose of measuring the bulk density and specific gravity were mixed with cow-dung and loaded into the third 15 L container. Following measurement of bulk density and specific gravity of each of the different sets of FVW, under individual and composite basis, the wet waste fraction was transferred into the primary 10 L container. Thereafter, on a weekly basis 1 L of the hydrolyzed product from the second 10 L container was transferred to the acidogenic chamber along with 500 ml of cow-dung slurry. This was usually done at the end of the week. At the start of the week, however, the leachate produced from the FVW fraction in the first chamber was transferred to the second 10 L container, and it was retained in the second hydrolytic chamber for 4–5 days.

Performance evaluation of batch digestion of OFMSW in the three-stage reactor :

In all the three systems loading was carried out separately i.e. under batch mode. In case of the first hydrolytic chamber vegetable waste was added from the top and the liquid portion from the previously loaded fraction, after it had undergone hydrolysis, was collected from the sample outlet at the bottom by squeezing the solid content (which had undergone hydrolysis) from the top. Thereafter the liquid content was transferred into the second hydrolytic chamber. Supernatant, equivalent to the volume of hydrolyzed fraction taken out from the methanogenic reactor and was added to the fresh vegetable waste, at the top chamber of the first hydrolytic container. This addition was done after extracting the hydrolyzed liquid from the bottom of the first chamber, such that the solid content was completely submerged. Thereafter the lid of the first chamber was kept closed for the entirety of the batch period. The content in the second hydrolytic reactor was thoroughly mixed after addition of the liquid from the first chamber. Approximately four liters of the acidogenic content was taken out and kept inside 2.5 L jars each time the batch adjustment took place. Following this, the liquid level in the second hydrolytic container and in the third container i.e. the acidogenic chamber were ad-

justed by opening the valve connecting the two and after the level was adjusted the valve was closed and the content in the acidogenic reactor was mixed slowly using a glass rod. Next the supernatant, after some of it had been added to the first chamber, from the methanogenic chamber was taken out in such a way that the level was just below the effluent outlet provided at the top of the chamber. This content was again stored in 2.5 L jars. Following this procedure, 3.5 L of the acidogenic content was transferred into the methanogenic reactor every time a batch was set. Lastly, the content stored inside each of the 2.5 L jars were slowly emptied into the second hydrolytic chamber and the valve adjacent to the acidogenic chamber was again kept open until the liquid level in both the second and the third chamber was same.

The maximum organic load chosen for the first chamber, in a particular batch operation, was 1255 g whereas the minimum organic load was 273 g. The batch period chosen for a single batch operation was 96 h. The maximum number of sample collection in a single batch was 9. The maximum time interval between two consecutive sample collections in a single batch operation was 24 h, whereas the minimum was 6 h. Every time prior to sample collection from each of the three chambers the content was thoroughly mixed, excepting the methanogenic container, and the sample was collected from the top as well as from the bottom. Thereafter the analysis was performed using the filtered sample from each of the three containers. For the purpose of filtering, 30–40 ml of the collected sample was passed through a commercial filter paper each time. This was done in order to determine the sCOD of the collected sample. Temperature monitoring along with addition of nutrients such as phosphate buffer, ferric chloride, magnesium sulfate and calcium chloride (1 ml per liter content) were also done from time to time as part of the reactor monitoring.

As mentioned, the performance evaluation of the three-stage anaerobic reactor was done in batch mode. The batch studies were carried out in such a way that the organic loading rate (OLR) at the start of each batch was increased in a consistent manner for two to

three consecutive batches. Thereafter at the start of the third or fourth batch the OLR was again reduced to a particular amount and it was again gradually increased for the next few batches. This was done in order to check the reactor response to different batch periods for the low and the high OLR. In this way numerous batch studies were performed.

Results and discussion

Results of the characterization of FVW under individual and composite basis :

The results obtained from the characterization of fruit and vegetable wastes under individual basis have been shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows the characterization of FVW under composite basis.

There are plenty of evidences from available literatures that FVW is very much compatible to the process AD. From the literature¹² it can be seen that the bulk density in case of vegetable wastes (composite) has a range between 202–701 kg/m³, the typical value being taken as 359 kg/m³, whereas the results from our study indicate a range between 845–1003 kg/m³. In case of the moisture content the range found from the literature is in between 60–90%, the typical value being taken as 75%, whereas results from our study indicate the range to be within 83–93%. The disparity in the range for both the bulk density and the moisture content, in case of both composite vegetable wastes and fruit wastes, is due to the reason that in our study the range was specified using only 12 vegetable and fruit items, whereas the range mentioned in the literature has been supposedly found out by characterizing an even greater number of vegetable and fruit items. Apart from this, another reason which can be cited with regards to this disparity is that of the seasonal and climatic variation of the two different places where the characterization was performed. In addition, the different measurement techniques can be another reason which can mentioned in this regard. The reason for carrying out the characterization using such lesser number of fruit and vegetable items can be explained from the perspective of easier availability and low cost of the different selected items.

Table 1. Physical characterization of FVW under individual basis

Item	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Specific gravity	Loss of moisture (%)	Moisture content (%)	Fixed solids (%)	Volatile solids (%)
Potato	833.30–1070.26	0.833–1.070	14.00–19.30	70.00–76.50	1.64–2.00	98.00–98.36
Serpent gourd	743.26–925.15	0.743–0.925	27.30–27.80	93.03–93.30	0.85–1.10	98.90–99.15
Ash gourd	724.74–814.96	0.724–0.815	25.09–26.00	94.77–95.00	0.30–0.68	99.32–99.70
Asparagus beans/ cowpea	751.90–756.57	0.752–0.757	21.71–34.40	90.41–92.80	1.48–2.07	97.93–98.52
Okra	711.11–776.56	0.711–0.777	23.65–33.30	92.01–94.70	1.07–1.95	98.05–98.93
Ribbed gourd	828.28–844.93	0.828–0.845	26.27–29.30	93.33–94.70	0.84–2.04	97.96–99.16
Bitter gourd	833.30–890.36	0.833–0.890	12.00–25.61	62.00–91.25	1.58–4.00	96.00–98.42
Gourd	806.45–833.79	0.807–0.834	11.00–24.30	58.00–89.80	0.60–1.32	98.68–99.40
Papaya	922.70–985.60	0.923–0.986	13.12–28.43	90.13–93.45	0.72–0.81	99.19–99.28
Brinjal	641.03–740.66	0.641–0.741	17.30–28.88	92.70–93.71	1.09–1.19	98.81–98.91
Cucumber	949.44–862.24	0.949–0.862	27.88–23.33	96.00–97.00	0.38–0.49	99.51–99.61
Guava	922.67–923.37	0.923–0.924	11.47–26.00	84.55–92.00	0.20–1.39	98.61–99.80

Table 2. Physical characterization of FVW under composite basis

Item (Run no.)	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	Specific gravity	Loss of moisture (%)	Moisture content (%)	Fixed solids (%)	Volatile solids (%)
FVW (1)	868.91	0.869	14.70	82.90	0.90	98.91
FVW (2)	961.77	0.962	20.72	92.71	1.09	99.10
FVW (3)	1002.66	1.003	16.15	87.29	1.61	99.04
FVW (4)	844.76	0.845	14.82	86.37	0.96	98.39
Mean	919.525	0.920	16.598	87.318	1.140	98.860
Median	915.34	0.916	15.485	86.830	1.025	98.975
Variance	4211.938	0.0042	5.989	12.373	0.0783	0.0783
Standard deviation	64.899	0.0649	2.447	3.518	0.2799	0.2799

Batch results of the three-stage lab-scale mesophilic AD reactor :

Numerous batch studies were conducted out of which data from few relevant batches were taken. The results from the batch studies for the hydrolytic, acidogenic and methanogenic systems are shown in the pH profile for the three systems in Figs. 2, 3 and 4, whereas the alkalinity profile for the three systems have been given in Figs. 5, 6 and 7 respectively. Figs. 8, 9 and 10 represent the time dependent sCOD profiles for the three systems.

It can be seen from the graphical plots that the pH values for the three different systems were least in case of the hydrolytic system, highest in case of the methanogenic system and intermediate in case of the acidogenic system for a particular batch study.

Fig. 2. pH profile for hydrolytic batches.

Fig. 3. pH profile for acidogenic batches.

Fig. 4. pH profile for methanogenic batches.

This is due to the fact that every time a batch mode was set the hydrolytic reactor was loaded with the hydrolyzed liquid portion from the first reactor which was basically simple soluble organic matter or monomers comprising of amino acids and long chain fatty acids. This led to the decreased pH values of the hydrolytic second chamber in comparison to the other two. Another reason for this can be the least volume of the hydrolytic chamber (10 L) compared to the acidogenic (15 L) and the methanogenic chamber (22 L). While mass-balancing the contents of each

of the three reactors during the onset of each batch, the contents of the hydrolytic chamber got diluted the least due to the lowest reactor volume among the three.

As seen from the pH profiles, the pH range of the methanogenic system was between 7.5 and 8.2, for the acidogenic system the range was between 7.0 and 7.7, and in case of the hydrolytic system the range was in between 6.0 and 7.0. Even though this was in keeping with the idea that the methanogenic system should have the greatest pH range compared to the acidogenic system, which again should have a higher pH range compared to the hydrolytic system, the ideal pH range for either of the three-systems (ideal pH ranges for hydrolysis, acidogenesis and methanogenesis are 4.0–5.5, 5.5–6.5 and 6.8–7.8 respectively) was not achieved. Formation of CO₂ from VFAs, carried into the methanogenic chamber from the acidogenic chamber, can be cited as one of the reasons. CO₂ being an alkaline specie contributes to increase in the system pH. In the present study, the highest pH range in the methanogenic chamber was due to the breakdown of the VFAs to biogas, whereas in the acidogenic chamber breakdown of the long chain fatty acids (LCFAs) to VFAs occurred. In the hydrolytic chamber, production of both LCFAs and VFAs occurred, leading to the least pH range among the three. Hence it can be said that pH plays a significant role in the fermentation process brought about by bacterial activity³⁰. According to literature³¹, the ideal pH range for the growth of methanogenic bacteria is 6.8–7.8 which was unable to be maintained hence resulting in the poor reactor performance, especially in the methanogenic chamber.

In case of the alkalinity values, as seen from the three graphs (Figs. 5–7), the highest readings were obtained for the methanogenic chamber followed by the acidogenic chamber and the hydrolytic chamber. This can again be accounted due to the formation of CO₂ which was supposedly higher in case of the methanogenic and the acidogenic system than that of the hydrolytic system. CO₂ formation is primarily dictated by the presence of fatty acids concentration

Fig. 5. Alkalinity profile for hydrolytic batches.

Fig. 7. Alkalinity profile for methanogenic batches.

Fig. 6. Alkalinity profile for acidogenic batches.

which was again evidently higher in case of the acidogenic (4500–5900 mg/L as CaCO₃) and the methanogenic (4500–6500 mg/L as CaCO₃) chamber compared to the hydrolytic (2500–4500 mg/L as CaCO₃) chamber. The high pH values, supposedly due to low VFA concentration, in case of the methanogenic chamber also led to the increase in the alkalinity values. Since the buffering capacity of an AD system is basically a measure of the system alkali-

lity, it has to be ensured that the system alkalinity stays within the desirable range (7400–27000 mg/L as CaCO₃). For this addition of strong bases or carbonate salts may be done¹³, which removes the CO₂ by converting it into bicarbonate. The concentration of bicarbonate ions in an AD system thus plays a vital role in revealing the buffering capacity of the system, which is reduced significantly by the production of VFAs.

The sCOD values in each batch indicate that the hydrolytic chamber always had the highest concentration followed by the acidogenic chamber and the methanogenic chamber, at the start of each batch. The sCOD reduction profile from the graphs (shown in Figs. 8–10) show that substrate (sCOD) utilization rate was greatest in case of the acidogenic chamber followed by the methanogenic chamber and the hydrolytic chamber. However, despite significant sCOD reduction in the methanogenic chamber there was no appreciable indication of gas production noticed. This can be explained from the point of view of the imbalance caused by the high pH ranges and the toxicity (due to sulfides mainly) related to it. The reduction in the sCOD concentration may have been due to sulfate reduction along with the increased VFA concentration greater than the optimal value (< 1000

Fig. 8. sCOD profile for hydrolytic batches.

Fig. 9. sCOD profile for acidogenic batches.

mg/L) required for biogas production. The toxicity related to VFA was not revealed by the pH values, which were evidently high, mostly due to the reason that the VFAs got dissociated. Apart from that, the weak nature of VFAs (low pKa values) may also have had a minimal impact on the pH values (which were primarily dominated by the evolution of CO₂).

Fig. 10. sCOD profile for methanogenic batches.

There was obviously increase in the biomass growth, which had contributed to the reduction in sCOD values, but the sulfate reduction also could have had a significant impact in the sCOD utilization. When sulfate reduces to sulfide, some organic material (COD) acts as donor of electrons and receptor of oxygen. Certain vegetables (red beet, carrot, cabbage, tomato etc.), used in our study, contain significant concentration of sulfate which may have contributed to the aforesaid problem.

It is a well-known fact that the process of AD of organic waste is accompanied by the production of LCFAs or VFAs. The produced VFAs are converted to methane and carbon-dioxide under normal circumstances which usually results in the rise of the sCOD and pH values; however, if the conditions prevalent inside a particular methanogenic chamber, such as that in the present study, are not ideal for the methanogenic bacterial growth, then mere fermentation of the accumulated VFAs take place resulting in the increased CO₂ production compared to that of CH₄. This eventually results in further increase of pH accompanied by a lower concentration of dissociated VFA, as seen in the reactor in question.

It was possible to determine the substrate utilization rate for the hydrolytic system, the acidogenic

system and the methanogenic system using the sCOD reduction profile for each of the three systems, as shown in the figures from Fig. 11 to Fig. 21, and they are respectively 0.168 d⁻¹, 0.6 d⁻¹ and 0.56 d⁻¹. The average *k* values for the three systems were worked out in h⁻¹ and multiplied with 24 h to obtain the above mentioned substrate utilization rates, in day⁻¹. Selection of batches for working out the average substrate utilization rate was based on the *R*² values obtained for individual batches. Batches with *R*² ≥ 0.92 were chosen for better accuracy. The increase in the alkalinity values for different data in a single batch were supposedly on account of the

CO₂ production due to fermentation of the acetates.

sCOD reduction profile for various batch studies in case of the hydrolytic chamber :

From the *k* values of the given batches the average substrate utilization rate is worked out to be 0.007 h⁻¹. Multiplying this 0.007 h⁻¹ with 24 h gave the kinetic rate constant in day⁻¹, which is 0.168 d⁻¹.

Fig. 11. sCOD reduction profile for batch 2.

Fig. 12. sCOD reduction profile for batch 3.

Fig. 13. sCOD reduction profile for batch 4.

Fig. 14. sCOD reduction profile for batch 5.

sCOD reduction profile for various batch studies in case of the acidogenic chamber :

From the *k* values of the above given batches the

Fig. 15. sCOD reduction profile for batch 1.

Fig. 18. sCOD reduction profile for batch 4.

Fig. 16. sCOD reduction profile for batch 2.

Fig. 17. sCOD reduction profile for batch 3.

average substrate utilization rate is worked out to be 0.025 h^{-1} . Multiplying this 0.025 h^{-1} with 24 h gave the kinetic rate constant in day^{-1} , which is 0.6 d^{-1} .

sCOD reduction profile for various batch studies in case of the methanogenic chamber :

From the k values of the previous given batches the average substrate utilization rate is worked out to be 0.023 h^{-1} . Multiplying this 0.023 h^{-1} with 24 h gave the kinetic rate constant in day^{-1} , which is 0.56 d^{-1} .

The three-stage system enabled easier handling in terms of reactor loading, sample collection, individual chamber monitoring under batch mode, and also ensured that there was no contamination. Not only that, the physical separation of the different phases resulted in the increased rates of hydrolysis, acidogenesis and methanogenesis, without affecting the pH optimum to each phase. These apart the separate system also enabled easier adjustment of volume at the start of each batch. The production of methane was revealed upon opening of the valve attached to the third 5 L chamber and simultaneously holding a lighter which showed a clear blue flame.

Fig. 19. sCOD Reduction Profile for Batch 1.

Fig. 20. sCOD reduction profile for batch 2.

Fig. 21. sCOD reduction profile for batch 3.

Conclusion

- (i) The present study pertaining to a lab-scale three-stage anaerobic digester appropriately highlight, not only the efficiency of a three-stage reactor over one-stage and two-stage reactor but also sheds light on the need for AD compared to other classical methodologies, for the efficient management of Organic Fractions of Municipal Solid Wastes (OFMSW).
- (ii) It is a well-known fact that higher the moisture content of any particular waste item the faster was its hydrolysis potential and as such the hydrolysis results also indicated the same. Hydrolysis, being the rate limiting step in a three-stage AD process, is always required to be made rapid by the application of external addition of enzymes or water for that matter in case the hydrolysis potentiality of a particular item is poor. It was inferred from the hydrolysis study carried out on the different items that on an average a span of 5–14 days was necessary in order to attain 70% hydrolysis. Since the study was carried out using only a handful of FVW items it was impossible to draw a better conclusion in this regard. It was also inferred that composite OFMSW was ideal for adjusting the organic loading to the digester unit.
- (iii) The selection of a mesophilic temperature (30–40°C) regime was done conforming to literatures since it was revealed that work done in the past over thermophilic temperature (50–60°C) regime gave inconsistent results.
- (iv) The substrate that was used primarily composed of household FVW, conforming to literatures which revealed FVW to be the most suitable among the different types of other OFMSW, in terms of the rapidity rendered to the AD process.
- (v) The batch studies indicated significant sCOD reduction in all the three systems with the acidogenic reactor showing the highest substrate (COD) utilization rate followed by the

methanogenic reactor and the hydrolytic reactor.

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